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How many fragments? The original extent, nineteenth-century losses, and present size of the Swedish-Finnish medieval book fragment collections¹

Introduction

The National Archives of Sweden and the National Library of Finland have in their possession exceptionally large collections of medieval book fragments stemming from the same early modern context of parchment reuse. Starting in the late 1530s, King Gustav I (r. 1523–1560) reorganised the Swedish tax administration. The realm was divided into relatively small administrative units (Swe. *fögderi*, pl. *fögderier*), from which tax records were brought annually to the Royal Chamber in Stockholm for audit. Simultaneously, the central administration started to produce increasing quantities of records concerning customs, shipyards, military forces, and other functions directly under royal supervision. From the 1540s until the early decades of the seventeenth century, most of those records were bound in covers made of parchment sourced from medieval books, predominantly of liturgical content. Over 30 000 thousand of these book fragments now survive. The vast majority of them are divided between Stockholm and Helsinki, where accounts dealing with Finland were transferred after Sweden ceded Finland to Russia in 1809.²

1 This article has been written as part of a project that has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 948497 (BOMPAC, Books of the Medieval Parish Church).

2 The vast majority of the fragments (approximately three quarters) are housed in the Swedish National Archives in Stockholm, with most of the rest being found at the Finnish National Library in Helsinki. Additionally, minor collections of fragments stemming from the same context are also found in other Swedish (and to a lesser extent Finnish) libraries and archives, the British Library, and the Russian Academy of Sciences in St. Petersburg as well as smaller quantities in some university libraries across Europe and North America. On the archival history of the accounts and fragments in Sweden, see Brunius 2000 and 2013; for Finland, see Kerkkonen 1988; on leaves donated to the British Library, see Lehtinen 2005; concerning Slavonic fragments that have ended up in St. Petersburg, see Löfstrand 1984; and for more on early print fragments dispersed to libraries far and wide, see Wolodarski 2013.

The fragmentary religious books in the Stockholm and Helsinki repositories constitute the largest body of written evidence to survive from the Swedish and Finnish Middle Ages. They have significant, but only partially exploited, research potential.³ To a large extent, this potential is a function of the fragments' apparent representativeness regarding the medieval book resources of the Swedish realm. Scholars know that early modern officials often sourced parchment from the same region, or even locality, where the tax records were produced.⁴ The fragments thus offer a rare sampling of the book resources of one realm at the end of the Middle Ages. The collection can be (and has been) used qualitatively to study, e.g. the history of book production, liturgy, and religious life more generally.⁵ However, as a corpus it could be utilised to study even broader processes, such as Christianisation and the building of diocesan and parish organisations, or even state formation, which in Sweden proceeded in conjunction with the establishing of the Christian church.⁶

To effectively pursue these broader questions via the fragments, quantitative approaches are therefore required. To enable them, accurate data is needed about the size and composition of the collections. A starting point for such work is now available in the digital catalogues for most of the Stockholm and Helsinki fragments, published in the early 2010s.⁷ In this article, we use this data, together with other data sources, to advance a data-driven understanding of the Stockholm-Helsinki fragment collection as a corpus. Briefly stated, this article makes a limited but fundamental contribution to the *Quellenkunde* of the medieval, or Catholic-era, parchment book fragments preserved in Stockholm and Helsinki. Its central aims can be outlined as follows. Firstly, we reconstruct the original number of covers made of medieval parchment that existed in the 1630s when the Vasa-era account series ended and became a closed archival entity. Secondly, we provide a data-based description of the losses that this material has suffered at later stages. This will also enable the

3 On the collections, see Keskiäho 2008 a; Brunius 2013; Ommundsen & Heikkilä 2017; Heikkilä 2017.

4 On the sourcing of parchment, see Brunius 2013, 24–33.

5 See, e.g. Haapanen 1924; Maliniemi 1925; Schalin 1946; Knuutila 1984; Knuutila 1990; Brunius 1991; Helander 1991; Äikää 1995; Helander 2001; Taitto 2002; Gullick 2005; Lehtinen 2005; Toy 2005; Brunius 2008; Heikkilä 2008; Keskiäho 2008 b; Tahkokallio 2008; Toy 2009; Heikkilä 2010; Walta 2011; Gullick 2013; Heikkilä 2013; Walta 2013; Björkqvall 2015; Gullick 2017; Walta 2017; Raninen 2020; Supponen 2023.

6 Such approaches have been applied to some subsets of fragments already. See, e.g. Heikkilä 2009; Niskanen 2010; Niblaeus 2010.

7 The Stockholm fragments have been catalogued in the on-line *Medeltida pergamentomslag* (MPO) database, which also includes images of most of the fragments; see <https://sok.riksarkivet.se/MPO> [accessed 30 August 2024]. The Helsinki fragments form the *Fragmenta membranea* collection and can be found in digitised form at <https://fragmenta.kansalliskirjasto.fi/> [accessed 30 August 2024]. Both collections, which mainly include fragments of manuscript books, could be augmented by including a few thousand still uncatalogued early print fragments. These fragments are discussed in more detail later in this article.

future study of these losses in greater detail and on a regional level. Thirdly, we offer a new and more-accurate-than-previous calculation of the Stockholm and Helsinki fragment collections' present size. In other words, we seek to define the extent of early modern parchment recycling and create a foundation for further quantitative research on the fragments.

From the point of view of fragment scholarship, the most important contribution of our article concerns the representativity of the fragments vis-à-vis the medieval book resources from which they were sourced. This question has, unsurprisingly given its centrality, also attracted some previous scholarship. Mostly, prior studies have concentrated on how biased or un-biased the early modern 'sampling' of medieval books was.⁸ However, it is well known that a significant proportion of the parchment-covered Vasa-era accounts were destroyed in the 1807 Kammararkivet fire in Stockholm.⁹ Any consideration of how the remaining fragments relate to the book resources of the Swedish realm at the end of the Middle Ages thus necessitates a preliminary step: establishing how large the fragment collection originally was and estimating how much – and, if possible, what – has been lost. While the fire of 1807 is widely known and its impact acknowledged, its consequences have been analysed in only one article, *Jan Brunius's 'Landskapshandlingar i Kammararkivet. Från kammerens register till databas'*, from 2000.¹⁰ Despite its ground-breaking nature, the article, which focuses strictly on the accounts, does not provide a comprehensive enough vantage point for scholars seeking to understand the implications of their losses for the attached fragments. This lack of discussion largely stems from the fact that the data on which the article was based were not (quite understandably given the date of the article) published. Furthermore, the data now seem irretrievable. To complement *Brunius's* analysis, we re-examine the losses and publish novel data that will enable taking them, and their implications, into account in future studies of the fragments.

Our contribution is based on data that is available in existing databases, interpolated from previous research, and constructed through archival work.¹¹

8 On the size- and material-related biases of Nordic parchment recycling, see Wolodarski, Brunius, & Björkvall 2002; Brunius 2013, 38; Heikkilä 2017, 84, 102; Ommundsen & Heikkilä 2017, 5.

9 See Wichman 1991, 33. See also Kromnow 1950, 187. *Brunius* casts some doubt on whether the *Fogderäkenskaper* survived an earlier fire (1802) fully intact, as *Kromnow* claims; see Brunius 2000, 24.

10 Brunius 2000.

11 Our data has been prepared as part of the ERC-funded *Books of the Medieval Parish Church* project, hosted by the Finnish National Library and coordinated by Dr *Jaakko Tahkokallio*. We would like to thank our colleagues and research assistants for their work on the data, especially Dr *Holger Kaasik*, whose comprehensive re-working of the MPO data has greatly facilitated its research use.

The data we have used are published in conjunction with this article.¹² Since the article focuses on data, sources, and methods, we do not present them in detail here. Instead, the relevant source materials, data, and approaches are discussed as they are introduced. They are the protagonists of our contribution, rather than the means for reaching other aims, and will thus occupy centre stage. It should however be noted that our analysis of the data is descriptive by nature, and we have not attempted any statistical modelling. We will return to the methodological context of the article and how it relates to broader trends visible in the use of quantitative approaches in the humanities in our conclusions.

Before moving on to the subject matter, some key terms require clarification. Unless otherwise specified, the word ‘fragment’ refers to a single parchment object stemming from a medieval book (manuscript or early print), usually in the form of a single leaf or a bifolium. It should be noted that the word has, in previous research, sometimes been used of fragmentarily preserved books (in the sense of a ‘book fragment’), consisting of several separate parchment objects. This usage has had currency especially in discussions of the Helsinki collection, which has been catalogued as reconstructed codices rather than individual fragments.

According to our terminology, the fragments in question have survived as ‘covers’ of account booklets. We prefer the term ‘cover’ to ‘wrapper’, the other English word often used in this context. This is because the parchment was normally attached to the spine of the account booklet by sewing, resulting in a binding known as a ‘stitched binding’ or ‘longstich binding’ in the context of the history of bookbinding. ‘Cover’ is the standard term for the fixed front and back coverings of books and booklets, regardless of their material, whereas the term ‘wrapper’ most commonly and logically refers to detachable types of covering.¹³

To refer to covers made of reused medieval parchment, typically consisting of one, but sometimes of several, fragments, we have used the term ‘parchment cover’. It should be noted that a minority of the account booklets actually had covers made of newly produced (rather than recycled medieval) parchment. When we have felt the need for semantic accuracy in this respect, we have added qualifiers, resulting in expressions such as ‘covers made of medieval / newly-produced parchment’.

12 The data can be found at the Zenodo repository.

See <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13879587>. The data set contains three data files, an appendix summarising the data, and a readme file.

13 On stitched bindings, see Pickwoad 2000, 4. *Ligatus: Language of Bindings*, the leading English-language vocabulary for bookbindings, uses the word ‘wrapper’ only in reference to coverings not sewn in place; see <http://w3id.org/lob/concept/1300>.

The original extent of the fragment collection

The parchment covers of the Vasa-era accounts did not attract researchers' attention before the mid-nineteenth century, and their cataloguing only started in the 1910s.¹⁴ Thus, there is no documentation of the medieval book fragments from before the 1807 fire. Fortunately for researchers, however, the *accounts* were catalogued more than once before this fateful event. The process for approximating the original number of fragments is thus straightforward. Firstly, the original number of account booklets needs to be calculated using pre-fire catalogues. Secondly, an estimate of how many of the booklets originally had a cover made of reused medieval parchment needs to be created.¹⁵

The best basis for calculating the original number of account booklets is provided by two catalogues, produced in 1628 and (presumably) 1637, respectively, i.e. immediately after the Vasa-era records effectively became closed archival entities.¹⁶ The first catalogue, '*Stockholm, Riksarkivet, Kammarens ämbetsarkiv, D II Ser I:1*', provides a year-by-year list of all the regional tax account booklets for the whole realm, including the Finnish provinces. The second catalogue, '*Stockholm, Riksarkivet, Kammarens ämbetsarkiv, D II Ser I:4*', lists those records that relate to functions of the royal central administration or regional centres of ducal governance.¹⁷ The largest group of accounts stemming from the central contexts are customs records, treasury records, storage records, records of shipyards, and various military records.

Whether looking at the regional or central accounts, a comparison of present archival metadata and the catalogues from 1628 and 1637 indicates that the seventeenth-century catalogues documented the collection with a high

14 The cataloguing of the Swedish fragments was advanced in 1914 when *Isak Collijn* published a report on his inventory of the material. The decision to begin cataloguing the fragments was made in the 1920s, and the work was begun in 1930 by *Toni Schmidt*. In Finland, the first catalogues were published by *Toivo Haapanen* (1922, 1925, 1932), who began his work in the late 1910s.

15 While we consistently discuss *parchment* fragments, it should be noted that at least a few dozen of the surviving covers were made of paper leaves sourced from manuscripts. Their number is, however, so small that we make no distinction between paper and parchment covers here.

16 The former catalogue, despite being dated to 1628, continues much beyond this point and was obviously kept in use after first being compiled. The latter is not dated, but the account series it contains extend to 1637 at the latest. *Jan Brunius* also assumes the catalogue is likely from that year. See Brunius 2000, 18, and note 37.

17 The sons of Gustav Vasa (and also some of his grandsons) received large apanages, known as duchies (Swe. *hertigdöme*) in Swedish research. They existed for varying lengths of time and, to a varying degree, had their own central administrations. The most important ones were the Duchy of Johan (parts of Finland, 1556–1563), the Duchy of Karl (Närke, Södermanland, and some western regions, 1560–1590s), the Duchy of Magnus (primarily western Östergötland, 1560–ca. 1570) and the Duchy of Erik (parts of Småland, 1558–1560). See, e.g. Backhaus et al. 1995, 104–107.

level of precision.¹⁸ Our calculation, based on manually counting accounts in the seventeenth-century catalogues, places the original number of regional account booklets at 37 691 and that of the central records at 6 026, giving a total of 43 717 booklets for the whole collection, stored throughout the seventeenth century at the Royal Palace in Stockholm.¹⁹ The distribution of all the accounts over time is presented in Figure 1, which shows that the number of booklets produced per year varied considerably (as did, therefore, the need for binding material), ranging from almost a thousand at most to approximately 400 on average. The changes primarily reflect administrative reforms and the resulting changes in the number of bailiwicks (Swe. *fögdrier*) over time, also shown in the figure.

Figure 1: The production of account booklets, 1537–1630, and the number of bailiwicks²⁰

18 Some discrepancies do appear, with one notable group being some of the military records from the early seventeenth century (e.g. *Militieräkenskaper*, Riksarkivet, Stockholm). These records, however, do not seem to have had covers made of medieval parchment (the current fragment metadata shows no connection to seventeenth-century records in these series), and they have thus been excluded from the present study. Additionally, it should be noted that there are some private accounts with parchment covers that inevitably fall outside any catalogues of the crown administration. One example are the accounts of the Bielke family (*Bielkesamlingen*, Riksarkivet, Stockholm), but they, and any others like them, amount to no more than a few dozen accounts and are thus insignificant for any quantitative discussion.

19 These figures include account booklets up to and including the year 1630, after which the use of parchment covers became quite rare. The 1628 catalogue lists records by the provinces included in the modern *Landskapshandlingar* collection as well as Finland. In addition, two smaller series are listed: one for Livland (1 277 accounts) and one for the 1613 *Älvsborg lösen* (199 accounts).

20 Data on the booklets: Stockholm, Riksarkivet, Kammarens ämbetsarkiv, D II Ser I:1 and I:4. Data on the bailiwicks: Hallenberg 2001, 91; Almquist 1917–1922, III (tables).

Knowing the number of account booklets that were produced, the question then becomes, how many of them were bound in covers made of repurposed medieval parchment. It is well known that towards the end of the period under discussion, more and more booklets were supplied with a cover made of newly-produced parchment or lacked one completely.²¹ However, no attempt has ever been made to quantify how common this practice was, and it also cannot be taken for granted that all earlier booklets had covers made of medieval parchment. To reliably estimate the proportion of accounts covered with recycled parchment, a physical examination of large quantities of surviving account booklets might seem like the most obvious way forward. The later history of the collections, however, renders this approach ineffective. In Helsinki, all parchment fragments have been removed from the accounts and are now kept separately in the National Library, while the accounts are preserved in the National Archives. In Stockholm, most accounts still have their parchment covers in place, but even there, approximately 3 000 parchment covers made of manuscripts and roughly 1 300 parchment covers made of early printed books (mostly incunabula) have been removed.²² Hence, there is little reason to adopt this laborious method knowing *prima facie* that the accuracy of the count would be severely compromised.

We must therefore start by examining the cataloguing information rather than the physical material. In brief, we need to be in a position to compare the total number of parchment covers with the total number of account booklets in the surviving collections. For such a comparison, precise numbers for both are needed. Since the accounts are catalogued in Riksarkivet's NAD database, the first logical step might be to turn to present-day archival metadata to establish the current number of account booklets.²³ Unfortunately, however, the available metadata does not itemize each booklet, instead cataloguing the material only as annual 'units'. Each unit usually comprises the records of one bailiff from a single year, amounting to approximately three to six booklets not enumerated in the metadata.²⁴

Thus, the best available metadata on the account booklets is still provided by the seventeenth-century catalogues. When studying them another obvious complication is however encountered. Due to the damage caused by the 1807 fire, the catalogues no longer accurately reflect all parts of the collection. Fortunately, though, the fire left large chronological segments from many

21 Brunius 2013, 26–27.

22 Wolodarski (Wolodarski, Brunius, & Björkqvall 2002, 203–204) estimates the quantity of removed early prints at 2 500 leaves. Since most, but not all, covers were made of bifolia, we put the estimate at 1 300.

23 *Nationell arkivdatabas* (NAD), found at <https://sok.riksarkivet.se/nad> [accessed 30 August 2024].

24 While the booklets were indeed counted in a conservation project in the 1990s (see Brunius 2000), the data are now inaccessible.

geographical areas untouched (while essentially wiping out others). For the segments surviving in good condition, the seventeenth-century catalogues still provide accurate descriptions. Furthermore, the above-mentioned 'unit-based' metadata on NAD can be used to identify these segments since the same organisation by unit is also present in the seventeenth-century catalogues (which in addition itemise each booklet). While the correspondence is not perfect – some material has been moved between subcollections and the definition of a unit appears to vary slightly – it is close enough for identifying the years and regions of the account series that have either survived in full or in very good condition. They include: the Diocese of Skara, 1570–1690 and 1611–1630; Småland, 1539–1579 and 1611–1630; Östergötland, 1580–1600; the Diocese of Västerås, 1569–1584; the Diocese of Strängnäs, 1585–1600; Uppland, 1537–1553; Norrland, all records; and Finland, all records. In addition, the central records have also completely survived. Therefore, with respect to the above collection segments, the seventeenth-century catalogues still provide reliable figures for the numbers of account booklets existing today.

To examine the proportion of accounts in these segments that had covers made of recycled parchment, we added a second data component: the number of surviving fragments associated with the accounts. This involved using two very different processes, one for the Stockholm material and another for the Helsinki material. For the Stockholm fragments, the information on their connections to the accounts has been retrieved from the Riksarkivet's *Medeltida pergamentomslag* database (MPO).²⁵ This archival database makes available the cataloguing information of all medieval parchment fragments in the Stockholm repositories, excluding most of the fragments stemming from early printed books. While it does not contain structured metadata on the fragments' association with the accounts, the archival identifier of most fragments includes such information in a text string (e.g. Fr 1: 'Östergötlands handlingar. 1539:2:1'). When working with a spreadsheet of MPO metadata provided by Riksarkivet, it was uncomplicated to divide the information into separate fields in our own dataset. Such metadata does not, however, exist for those Stockholm fragments that were removed from the accounts in the nineteenth century. Furthermore, it is important to keep in mind the estimated 1 300 early print covers that were removed and taken to other archival contexts and are thus not listed at all in the MPO database. Nevertheless, the data still allows for valuable observations.

25 See <https://sok.riksarkivet.se/MPO> [Accessed 30 August 2024].

The ratios of account booklets to fragments for the aforementioned spatio-temporal segments are shown in Table 1. Since our data clearly demonstrates – in line with observations presented in previous research – that the use of medieval parchment began to decline around the year 1610, we shall divide the examination into pre- and post-1610 segments.

Table 1: Account booklets and fragments for select temporal segments, by area²⁶

	Diocese	Area	Time period	Account booklets (1628)	Frs. (MPO)	Ratio (%)
Estimates up to 1610	Skara	Västergötland, Värmland, and Dalsland	1570–1590	1 192	1 129	94,71 %
	Linköping/Växjö	Småland	1539–1579	2 501	2 317	92,64 %
	Linköping	Östergötland	1580–1600	1 085	983	90,60 %
	Uppsala	Norrland (without Åland and Österb.)	1540–1610	1 393	1 099	78,89 %
	Västerås	Västmanland and Dalarna	1569–1584	1 048	745	71,09 %
	Strängnäs	Södermanland and Närke	1585–1600	738	518	70,19 %
	Uppsala	Uppland	1537–1553	688	427	62,06 %
	n/a	Central accounts	1530–1610	5 450	3 435	63,03 %
Estimates post-1610	Uppsala	Norrland (without Åland and Österb.)	1611–1620	155	77	49,68 %
	Linköping/Växjö	Småland	1611–1630	590	243	41,19 %
	Skara	Västergötland, Värmland, and Dalsland	1611–1630	690	278	40,29 %
	Västerås	Västmanland and Dalarna	1611–1630	592	102	17,23 %
	Uppsala	Uppland	n/a			n/a
	Strängnäs	Södermanland and Närke	n/a			n/a
	Linköping	Östergötland	n/a			n/a
	n/a	Central accounts	1611–1630	575	120	20,87 %

Two important observations can be made based on the information in the table. Firstly, the share of accounts covered with reused parchment was much lower in 1611–1630 than in the sixteenth-century account segments, indicating that the use of medieval parchment declined sharply in the seventeenth century. The rate of this decline can be illustrated with more detailed diagrams for the records of Småland and the Diocese of Skara (Västergötland, Värmland, and Dalsland), as shown in Figure 2. The figure reveals that the use of medieval parchment declined quickly in the 1610s and was already quite low by the 1620s.

²⁶ Account booklets counted from the 1628 catalogue (Stockholm, Riksarkivet, Kammarens ämbetsarkiv, D II Ser I:1) and fragments from the MPO.

Figure 2: Account booklets and fragments, Småland and the diocese of Skara, 1600–1630.²⁷

Secondly, the figures for 1540–1610, the period of intense parchment reuse, are high but also contain significant variation. In several areas, well over ninety per cent of the accounts appear to have had a cover made of medieval parchment, but for others the figures drop to eighty, seventy, or even close to sixty per cent. Were accounts from some regions really covered with reused parchment less frequently, or are we encountering deficiencies in the data? The latter seems to be the case. As already mentioned, the dataset is clearly lacking in one respect: the great majority of the early print covers detached from the regional accounts of modern-day Sweden are not included in the MPO database.²⁸ *Anna Wolodarski* has estimated that 2 500 leaves were removed in the nineteenth century, which, given that many of them constitute bifolia, implies perhaps approximately 1 300 individual covers.²⁹ Notably, all regions that have a low number of fragments in proportion to accounts belong to the Svealand dioceses, for which printed large-format liturgical books were produced before the Reformation. Västerås had a printed gradual (a large-format book eminently suitable for reuse as covers), Strängnäs a printed missal, and Uppsala (to which also Norrland belonged) two different missals and a manual. Furthermore, we know that fragments of the diocese-specific printed

27 Data sources: see previous footnote. Data series: 1 230 booklets, 830 fragments (Småland); 1 220 booklets, 774 fragments (Diocese of Skara).

28 For the most comprehensive discussion of the removed Swedish early print fragments, see *Wolodarski 2013*.

29 We have not been able to count the leaves in full, but it is clear that the number of fragments found just in Kungliga biblioteket's reconstructed early printed books is significant, i.e. ca. 700: two specimens of *Missale Upsalense Vetus* (Diocese of Uppsala, 1484, ca. 244 leaves), one of *Missale Strengnense* (Diocese of Strängnäs, 1487, ca. 277 leaves), one of *Manuale Upsalense* (Diocese of Uppsala, 1487, ca. 94 leaves), one of *Graduale Arosiense* (Diocese of Västerås, 1493, 226 leaves), and one of *Missale Upsalense novum* (Diocese of Uppsala, 1513, 241 leaves). See *Collijn 1934–1938*, 30–31, 71, 235.

books became associated primarily with accounts from the same region, and secondarily with accounts from the rest of Svealand.³⁰

Given the obvious data-related explanation for the lower relative numbers of fragments associated with Svealand accounts, it seems well warranted to assume that the material from Östergötland, the Diocese of Skara, and Småland is much more likely to present a realistic picture of the ratio of accounts to fragments. Furthermore, it is important to remember that, in addition to the early print fragments excluded from the MPO database, approximately 3 000 fragments that are in MPO lack enough metadata for their link to the accounts to be considered. Thus, even in those regions, the real quantity of covers made of medieval parchment may be higher than the table indicates. On the other hand, the ratios are slightly inflated by the fact that the table incorporates *fragments*, not *covers*, which sometimes were composed of more than one individual fragment. With such caveats in mind, a rough estimate that more than 90 per cent of accounts had a cover made of medieval parchment before 1610, and more than 40 per cent after it, seems warranted.

Before trying to establish a more definitive numeric estimate for the average proportion of accounts covered with reused medieval parchment, let us also examine the Helsinki accounts and fragments. While information on the number of Helsinki accounts is easily retrievable from the early modern catalogues, it is a much less straightforward process to calculate the corresponding number of parchment covers. Firstly, such difficulty is a consequence of the physical separation of the accounts and fragments in the nineteenth century without documenting their connections. Secondly, the manuscript fragments in the Helsinki collection have not been catalogued as fragments, but rather as reconstructed codices, and the early print fragments related to the Finnish accounts have not been catalogued at all. To establish the needed metadata, we have, therefore, conducted a manual survey of all manuscript fragments in Helsinki (the *Fragmenta membranea* collection) as well as the relevant early

30 For those diocesan early print fragments that are still connected to the accounts and hence found in the MPO database, the proportions are as follows: *Missale Strengnense* (179 frs), 55.31% in accounts from the diocese; 16.20% in accounts from the rest of Svealand; 16.76% unknown; 11.73% from other parts of the realm; *Missale Upsalense novum* (379 frs) 54.88% in accounts from the diocese; 13.19% in accounts from the rest of Svealand; 16.09% unknown; 15.83% in accounts from other parts of the realm; *Missale Upsalense vetus* (111 frs) 38.74% in accounts from the diocese; 11.71% from the rest of Svealand; 10.81% unknown; 38.74% in accounts from other parts of the realm.

print fragments,³¹ itemising each fragment for research purposes. This effort has not only provided us with an accurate number of covers in the collections, but also with some additional metadata not available for the Stockholm fragments.

The additional metadata concerns the relationship between a 'fragment' (i.e. a single physical piece of parchment) and a 'cover'. While most of the account covers were composed of a single fragment (a bifolium or a large single leaf cut off and folded), some covers were constructed by sewing together smaller pieces of parchment or else contained, in addition to the main cover component, smaller strips to support the binding. Most of the smaller pieces are identified as separate fragments in the MPO, even though they never constituted a cover in their own right. Of the 6 663 Finland-related parchment fragments, we have identified 5 892 as representing the primary portion of a cover. On the other hand, 485 fragments appear to represent secondary parts of covers (usually the back cover), while 286 smaller pieces were likely used to support the binding in some way. In other words, approximately 12 per cent of the present Helsinki fragments did not constitute the main part of a cover, and a single fragment thus appears to represent roughly 0.88 covers.³²

Concerning the broader question of how many of the accounts had covers made of medieval parchment, an examination of our data on the Finnish collection should offer the best chance of obtaining an overall picture since all the data categories should essentially be complete (no losses, early print covers included, covers separated from supportive parchment pieces). The 1628 catalogue lists 6 559 Finnish booklets, and there are currently an estimated 6 424 corresponding booklets at the National Archives. Given certain inherent inaccuracies in formulating the latter number, we can assume a near perfect survival rate for the Finnish accounts and use the 1628 catalogue as representative of the current archival situation.³³ Of the 6 559 booklets, 5 639 concern the years 1530–1610 and 920 the years 1611–1630. If we can assume, to choose

31 The early print fragments that we consider relevant here are those that have likely been used to cover accounts concerning Finland. Most of them are found as loose leaves at the National Library in Helsinki. In addition, however, there are three copies of *Missale Aboense*, a liturgical book for the Diocese of Åbo very likely repurposed almost exclusively for covers of Finnish accounts, 'reconstructed' from former account covers. One such copy is preserved at the National Library, another at the Jyväskylä University Library, and a third at the Kungliga biblioteket in Stockholm.

32 Given the uncertainties regarding such an estimate, we suggest using a 0.9 ratio for covers per fragment.

33 The figure of 6 424 has been arrived at by taking the overall number of listed account booklets up to the year 1630 (7 124; 7 291 overall) and deducting the booklets in the *Allmänna räkenskaper* series (700 up to 1630; 750 overall) that contain records relating to the central administration. Additionally, there are still perhaps approximately 200 booklets concerning Finland at the Riksarkivet in Stockholm, which would bring our figure almost on par with the 1628 catalogue.

a working hypothesis in line with the ratios given for other well-preserved regions, that 94 per cent of the booklets up to 1610 had a cover, and 44 per cent of the later ones, we end up with a figure of 5 705 covers.³⁴ As mentioned above, 5 892 covers are related to the Finnish accounts – some 200 more – but they also include covers from the series *Allmänna räkenskaper*, consisting of 750 booklets, but to which we have only thus far been able to connect 199 covers. Deducting those covers from the total would give us practically the same number of covers today as in our estimate.³⁵ The ratio of Finnish account booklets to covers made of medieval parchment would then be well in line with what the data suggest for areas like Småland and Östergötland.

The account to fragment ratios were surely not entirely identical in different regions, nor perhaps in the central administration's own records. We have estimated the ratios for each account segment listed in the early modern catalogues based on the evidence given above as well as a consideration of what can be validated through an analysis of the later losses and current archives (see the following sections). We estimate that, on the level of the whole realm, covering all account categories, approximately 93 per cent of the accounts were supplied with a cover made of medieval parchment before 1611, and approximately 43 per cent from that date onwards, bringing our overall estimate of the number of covers made of medieval parchment by roughly 1630 to approximately 37 500.³⁶ The figure for the ratio of fragments to account booklets before 1611 (93 per cent) may seem low, especially given that scholars have often assumed that practically all those booklets had covers made of medieval parchment. If it were higher, however, we would have to assume a greater number of parchment covers today than we can account for. In part, the figure may be explained by the fact that it is possible that two booklets were sometimes preserved within one cover (a loose booklet inside the binding of another booklet), thereby lowering the ratio. For details on our calculations of the original numbers of accounts and parchment covers, we refer you to a summary in our dataset.

34 $5\,639 \times 0.94 = 5\,300$ and $920 \times 0.44 = 405$.

35 The 199 covers for the central series seems low, but it could be explained by the fact that almost half of the accounts are from the seventeenth century and thus have fewer covers made of medieval parchment. This would have to be studied more as the *Allmänna räkenskaper* is an artificial construct and its composition somewhat unclear. In any case, this number has little bearing on our overall figures.

36 Based on the two historical catalogues, 37 589 account booklets were produced by 1610 and 6 128 between 1611 and 1630. With the above-mentioned percentages for covers made of medieval parchment, we arrive at the rounded figure of approximately 37 500 ($0.93 \times 37\,589 + 0.43 \times 6\,128$). For estimates for specific series of booklets, see our data set.

The Losses of the 1807 fire of Kammararkivet

After the Vasa-era record series were discontinued around 1630, the records were stored in the Royal Castle in Stockholm. A late eighteenth-century inventory demonstrates that the accounts and their covers survived the great 1697 Royal Castle fire virtually intact.³⁷ The material also seems to have escaped the Riddarholm archival fire in 1802 with relatively minor damages.³⁸ However, by 1807 their luck had run out. A new fire, almost certainly the result of drunken carelessness, devastated the newly built premises of the archives on 28 March 1807, and this time the Vasa-era records suffered severely.³⁹

How many of the estimated 37 500 original covers made of medieval parchment were lost in the fire? The scale of the damage has previously only been considered from the perspective of the Swedish *Landskapshandlingar* collection, i.e. the regional records dealing with most of modern-day Sweden, still today preserved in the Riksarkivet, in Stockholm. Based on a comparison between the seventeenth-century catalogue and the results of a manual counting of the present-day account booklets undertaken in a conservation project in the 1990s, *Jan Brunius* has calculated that 36 per cent of these records were lost in the fire.⁴⁰ Since the other parts of the collection (Finnish records and central records) apparently did not suffer any damage, one might think that no further examination would be needed.

From the perspective of fragment scholarship, however, *Brunius's* examination leaves some significant gaps. Firstly, his article focuses on the accounts, not the parchment covers. This distinction may seem trivial, but it has some important implications partly because, as we have shown, not all accounts were covered with parchment from medieval books in the first place. Secondly, the article documents the distribution of the losses with only one chronological diagram for the whole *Landskapshandlingar* collection.⁴¹ While the article provides a list of the main gaps in the collection by region, the list does not enable a more detailed examination of how the damages are distributed spatiotemporally. Access to such information would, however, be important in light of recent research. It appears that there was significant chronological and geographical variation in the types of medieval books sourced for parchment. For instance, fragments associated with accounts from the 1550s come (on average) from earlier medieval books than those covering accounts from

37 The fire destroyed most of the Royal Library. The archive suffered only minor damages, but apparently parts of it went into disarray as a result of the hectic rescue operation. See Wichman 1991, 33.

38 See Kromnow 1950, 187. *Brunius* seems to think that the losses suffered at this stage could have been more significant than *Kromnow* indicates. See *Brunius* 2000, 24.

39 On the fire, see Wichman 1991.

40 *Brunius* 2000, 21–25.

41 *Brunius* 2000, 23.

the 1590s, and fragments associated with accounts from Västergötland differ from those associated with Norrland.⁴² Researchers thus need to know how the losses are distributed over time and place to determine what *kinds* of fragments have been lost. This limitation is related to a third, and in its own way more fundamental, problem, namely the unavailability of the data upon which *Brunius* based his study. The key data for the article (on the number of now-existing *Landskapshandlingar* account booklets) was not published together with the article, as was normal at the time of its publication, and at present the data seems irretrievable. Thus, all further work on the losses needs new data as its starting point. Fourthly, and finally, *Brunius's* article limits its examination to the Swedish *Landskapshandlingar* series. While it was indeed this segment of the Vasa-era records that absorbed the losses, they should nevertheless be assessed in relation to the entire Stockholm-Helsinki collection.

To complement *Brunius's* work, our examination of the 1807 losses approaches them in three parts: the regional accounts of Sweden (*Landskapshandlingar*), the central administration's accounts, and the Finnish collections. Each entity is problematic in its own way, with issues concerning the availability of modern archival data, the intermingling of the entities, parity between historical and modern collections, and disconnections between account and fragment data (due to the removal of covers). We shall first discuss those parts of the collection that have traditionally been assumed to survive in full.

Let us first look at the Finnish material. As necessary background, it should be noted that the accounts presently kept in Finland do not correspond to how Finland, as an administrative region, was defined when the records were composed and organised. Firstly, Österbotten and Åland were administratively handled as parts of Norrland in the Vasa-era. Their records were removed from the Norrland series when the collection was divided after 1809 and incorporated into the new 'Finnish' collection. Secondly, records that were produced by the central administration (e.g. military records) but that dealt with Finnish territory were treated similarly. Especially the latter fact causes some complications, to which we will need to return later.

The Finnish collection has been for long considered to have survived well and our examination confirms this idea.⁴³ The effectively complete survival of the Finnish records is demonstrated by the three data series that we have assembled. The first series contains the number of account booklets in 1628, as recorded in the catalogue of the same year (with the booklets for Åland and Österbotten taken from the Norrland series and added to the Finnish one). The second series represents the number of account booklets at the Finnish National Archives today, with the record series related to the central

42 An article on this topic is being prepared by the present writers.

43 A point noted by, e.g., *Birgitta Odén* already in the 1950s; see *Odén* 1955, 67.

administration removed. The third series documents the numbers of covers in our data on Finnish fragments (including early print fragments). This last series has been adjusted by removing those covers that possibly belonged to the central administration's record series and were integrated into the Finnish collection only in the aftermath of 1809.⁴⁴ As we can see from Figure 3, the data yields a straightforward conclusion. The number of accounts historically and today is near identical, and both series follow the same year-by-year volume, with no temporal gaps. The fragment series is also as expected: somewhat below the number of accounts – in part because of the approximately 500 covers that lack the metadata necessary to be shown here – but indeed quite closely mirroring the curvature of the account data before tapering off after 1610.⁴⁵

Figure 3: Account booklets and covers made of medieval parchment, Finland 1537–1630.⁴⁶

Scholars have also maintained that the central accounts survived in full. Just as is the case with the Finnish accounts, our examination confirms this assumption. The examination is facilitated by the fact that modern cataloguing of the central records, in contrast to that of the regional records (the *Landskapshandlingar*), itemises each booklet in the same way as the 1637 catalogue. Figure 4a

44 As the connections between the Finnish accounts and their covers are no longer known, it was not possible to identify all covers related to the central account series. The fragment data was therefore adjusted by deducting the number of account booklets in the central account series. Not all of these had covers made of medieval parchment originally, so from this point of view the graph slightly underestimates the number of covers.

45 These 500 covers lack data on the fiscal year of the account they are referring to and cannot thus be plotted on a chronological scale.

46 Data series: booklets 1628 (total 6 559), booklets 2024 (6 424), parchment covers (5 308 minus 700 central accounts).

shows the close correspondence between the two data series on account booklets. The match is admittedly not perfect, as the present archival metadata lists a somewhat *greater* number of booklets than the 1637 catalogue (6 026 in 1637, 7 096 in 2024), but the temporal correlation is still quite strong. The numerical disparity likely results either from re-arrangements made within the collection (division of archival units) or the adding of material not included in the original catalogue (or both). The fact that the mismatch is particularly notable in the post-1610 records might be taken to suggest the latter. Records from the 1610s and 1620s may have remained in active administrative use in the 1630s, when the catalogue was being composed, and might have been added to the static archival collection only later. This idea is, however, speculative. Another factor that complicates the comparison is, once again, the physical separation of the central records concerning Finland, which are included in the data series as an approximation.

The data series showing fragments also correlates closely with the 1637 and 2023 account series. That the number of fragments is clearly lower than that of the accounts is to be expected, since it is known that some covers have been removed from the collections covered by the MPO (especially early print fragments) and that others, which are included, lack the metadata necessary to be connected to the accounts. In this context, it is worth noting that most of the central accounts were composed in Stockholm, where liturgical books printed for the dioceses of Svealand were available as cover material. The repurposing of the printed books increased towards the end of the sixteenth century, and it is precisely in this period that the number of fragments drops in relation to the number of accounts. The decline in the use of medieval parchment as covers, starting as it does in the 1610s is, again, also evident. The correlation between accounts and fragments also holds up quite well inside individual series within the central records, as exemplified by Figures 4b and 4c, with the first showing a large (*Varuhus och Handling & Provianträkenskaper*)⁴⁷ and the other a medium-sized (*Klädkammarräkenskaper*) central series.

47 It is listed as one series in the 1637 catalogue, but as two separate series in the present NAD metadata: *Varuhus och handling* and *Provianträkenskaperna*.

Figures 4a/b/c: Account booklets of the central administration and relevant fragments, 1537–1630.⁴⁸

48 Data sources: *Account booklets 2024*: account booklets listed in the Swedish National Archives *Nationell arkivdatabas* (NAD) in the series corresponding (to the extent it is possible to determine) to those in the catalogue from the 1630s. Additionally, the booklets listed for the years 1600–1630 in the series *Militieräkningar* have been omitted (as our data appears to show almost no connection to medieval fragments for this series after 1600) and booklets in the *Allmänna räkenskaper*, a sub-series of *Fogderäkenskaper* in the Finnish National Archives, has been added. *Account booklets 1630s*: account booklets mentioned in the 1637 catalogue; *Current frs. with appropriate archival metadata*: Fragments in the MPO with metadata that links them to these accounts.

Finally, we come to the real losses of the 1807 fire, i.e. those parts of the regional records that are presently preserved in Stockholm and are known in modern research as the *Landskapshandlingar* collection. Figure 5 summarises our data on this part of the collection, and we need to start by explaining the nature of the five different data series. Firstly, we have the original number of account booklets, which derives directly from the 1628 catalogue. The second series – account booklets 1999 – has been interpolated from the diagram published in *Brunius's* 2000 article. As mentioned, although the article documents the number of account booklets counted as part of a 1990s conservation project, the numerical data behind it is not public or available. The third series gives the number of annual units (each including several booklets) as they are listed in the 1628 catalogue. The fourth series shows the number of the (more or less) same units in the present-day archival metadata. The fifth series documents the number of fragments that have MPO metadata linking them to the *Landskapshandlingar* series.

Figure 5: Account booklets, units, and fragments in the *Landskapshandlingar* collection, 1540–1630.⁴⁹

The overall picture for the losses of account booklets is almost identical to that provided by *Brunius*, since we are using the same data (almost, having done our own counting of the original number of accounts). We estimate that 35 per cent of the accounts and 36 per cent of the covers made of medieval

49 The sizes of the data series (1527–1630): Booklets 1628 (29 656); Booklets 1999 (19 229); Units 1628 (10 506); Units 2024 (8 254); Fragments (12 723; with appropriate metadata).

parchment have been lost, amounting to a rounded figure of 9 250 covers.⁵⁰ Some useful additional observations can also be made. First, we note that a comparison of the two unit-based series shows losses precisely in the same years as in the comparison of the two series of booklets. The units, consequently, serve as a reliable proxy for the temporal localisation of the losses, useful when booklet-based data is unavailable. However, the magnitude of the losses shown by the unit data series is smaller than that evinced by the booklet series. For instance, clearly less than half of the booklets from the late 1550s have survived, whereas more than half of the units still exist. The explanation for this discrepancy can be found in the partial destruction of many units. While the fire destroyed many account segments *in toto*, for many others some booklets from the unit remain. The survival of even one booklet has been enough to establish the existence of the unit in the present metadata.

This discrepancy between units and booklets is particularly acute in the second half of the 1550s, and, related to this fact, an interesting observation on the fragments can be made. Overall, the data series on fragments closely adheres to the series giving the present number of account booklets. However, the correlation is lower than usual in two periods: after 1606 and from approximately 1553 to approximately 1560. The tapering seen in the early seventeenth century clearly results from the diminishing use of repurposed parchment in the covers overall, but the earlier dip in numbers calls for a different explanation. Interestingly, the late 1550s anomaly coincides with the most severe losses and the greatest disparity between the booklet-based and the unit-based series. We would suggest that the relative paucity of fragments connected to the accounts from approximately 1553 to approximately 1560 is a consequence of the generally damaged state of even the surviving records from that period. The Stockholm collection contains quite a large (if unquantified) number of severely damaged fragments, which are often completely blackened by heat and smoke and have, in some cases, even shrunk notably. Such damaged fragments have always been removed from the accounts, and it is not possible to re-establish their connections to the accounts since any rubrics they might have had at one time are now unreadable. This suggests, in other words, that a significant proportion of all fragments without any account-related metadata in the MPO collection likely comes from accounts belonging to this period.

To finish the examination of the losses concerning the *Landskapshandlingar* collection, it is useful to look at them by decade, which makes it possible to comprehend their temporal concentration in concrete fashion. Table 2 shows that the account losses are heavily concentrated in the 1550s and 1560s. What

50 We calculated 29 656 account booklets in the *Landskapshandlingar* series originally, and assuming that 94 per cent of them had a cover before 1610, and 44 per cent afterwards, we arrive at rounded figures of 25 750 covers originally, 9 250 lost and 16 500 today.

is more, given the fact that the accounts from this era more often had covers made of medieval parchment than those from the seventeenth century, the proportionate loss of fragments from this period is even higher than that of the accounts. In fact, over half of all lost fragments (50.3%) were originally used to cover accounts from the 1550s and 1560s. In contrast, the lost seventeenth-century accounts included only a relatively small quantity of fragments due to the decline in repurposing medieval parchment, especially after 1610 (14.8% of accounts, but only 7.8% of fragments).

Table 2: Lost account booklets, by temporal segment, in the *Landskapshandlingar* collection.⁵¹

	Accounts 1628	Accounts 1999	Accounts lost	Accounts, share of lost	Frs., share of lost (estim.)
1540–1549	1 781	1 360	421	4,0 %	4,3 %
1550–1559	4 121	2 172	1 949	18,6 %	20,1 %
1560–1569	5 390	2 461	2 929	27,9 %	30,2 %
1570–1579	4 021	2 681	1 340	12,8 %	13,8 %
1580–1589	3 697	2 693	1 004	9,6 %	10,4 %
1590–1599	3 101	1 812	1 289	12,3 %	13,3 %
1600–1609	3 007	2 577	430	4,1 %	4,4 %
1610–1619	2 602	2 108	494	4,7 %	2,6 %
1620–1630	1 881	1 257	624	6,0 %	0,8 %
	29 601	19 121	10 480	100,0 %	100,0 %

When conducting research on the fragments, an awareness of how the losses affect accounts from different Swedish provinces is even more important than knowledge of their chronology. This fact is addressed by the diagrams in Figure 6. Here, the data is grouped by administrative region, as they were defined when the material was catalogued in the seventeenth century. Three of the regions correspond to a single province (Swe. *landskap*; Uppland, Småland, Östergötland) and another three to medieval and early modern dioceses covering two or more provinces (Skara, Strängnäs, Västerås), while one of them covers an entire Swedish *landsdel* (Norrland). Regarding Norrland, it is worth reminding that the records concerning Österbotten and Åland, which belonged to the administrative region in early modern times, have been removed together with the rest of the Finnish accounts.

⁵¹ Data sources: The 1628 catalogue (Accounts 1628); Brunius 2000 / our dataset (Accounts 1999).

The data types for the regions are the same as above for the *Landskapshandlingar* overall, except for one important difference. Our only source for data on the present number of account booklets is the summary provided by *Brunius's* article from 2000. Since this summary does not give data for the individual administrative regions, but only the aggregate for all of them, we do not have account booklet data for the regions. We do, however, have data on the units, which – as we have seen – serve as a reliable proxy. Indeed, when we look at individual regions, we see a very strong correlation between archival units and fragments as they are today.

The temporal placement of the losses is broadly similar, although somewhat more precisely defined, compared to how the gaps are delineated in *Brunius's* article.⁵² The main improvement is that we can now also estimate the severity of the gaps and have the data, which are made public in conjunction with this article. The data provide a starting point for critically and quantitatively examining the representativeness of the fragment material from different parts of the realm. The losses are very substantial for some regions, and an awareness of them is of particular importance for all studies concerning the medieval manuscript culture of Svealand and, only to a slightly lesser degree, Östergötland. We shall return to the question of how this information may be used in the conclusions.

⁵² Brunius 2000, 24–25.

Figure 6: Account booklets, units, and fragments, by region, in the *Landskapshandlingar* collection.⁵³

⁵³ For details on the data, see our dataset.

The size of the current fragment collections

We conclude our analysis of the fragments by considering one final topic: the present number of medieval book fragments in the Stockholm and Helsinki fragment collections. This is an area that, despite its apparent simplicity, has a somewhat complicated research history of its own. To the best of our knowledge, the first estimate on the size of the fragment collections was provided by *Edward Grönblad*, who in 1846 estimated the number of covers in the Helsinki collection at 6 000.⁵⁴ In Sweden, the first well-founded estimate was provided by *Isak Collijn*, who published an inventory of the Kammararkivet collection in 1914 and estimated that it contained approximately 15 000 covers made of medieval parchment (29 000 leaves).⁵⁵ Soon after *Collijn's* inventory, a proper cataloguing of the accounts began in both Helsinki and Stockholm, but it did not quickly lead to a more accurate awareness of the overall sizes of the collections. *Toivo Haapanen*, who catalogued the liturgical material in Helsinki in the 1920s, repeated *Grönblad's* (fairly accurate) estimate of 6 000 covers for the Helsinki collection, which he then amended to include approximately 10 000 leaves. Haapanen also gave an estimate of 'something over 30 000 leaves' for the entirety of the Stockholm material (drawing on *Collijn* but apparently underestimating the number of covers existing outside of Kammararkivet and not accounted for in *Collijn's* survey).⁵⁶ *Toni Schmid*, who was at the time cataloguing the material in Stockholm, gave estimates that proved widely off the mark, underlining the difficulty of grasping the full scale of the collections containing fragments. In a 1933 *Scandia* article, she quoted estimates putting the size of the Kammararkivet collection at 35 000 covers (not leaves) and that of all Swedish collections together at more than 50 000 covers (more than double the actual amount).⁵⁷ *Schmid's* cataloguing project, called *Corpus Codicum Mutilorum* (CCM), and later continued by *Oloph Odenius*, did not apparently produce any calculation of the total number of fragments or covers, and in a 1993 article *Jan Brunius*, who was just becoming acquainted with the material, could only say that there were at least 17 000 covers made of medieval parchment.⁵⁸

It was only in the 2000s, as the cataloguing of the material started to approach completion, that better estimates were established. *Schmid's* and

54 Grönblad 1846, 223.

55 Collijn's work did not cover all fragment collections, leaving out smaller entities in places such as *Krigsarkivet* and *Slottsarkivet*. He was, however, aware of not only those collections but also collections in Denmark, Norway, and Finland, and, understanding the vital link between the Swedish and Finnish material especially, called for collaboration across borders. See Collijn 1914, esp. 12, 69, 74.

56 Haapanen 1922, xviii.

57 Schmid 1933, 104.

58 Brunius 1993, 15.

Odenius's CCM project was followed by another one, led by *Jan Brunius*, called *Medeltida pergamentomslag* (MPO). The project began in 1995 and brought the cataloguing to an end in 2003.⁵⁹ The MPO catalogue lists 22 909 fragments, but scholars have always known that some fragments were entered twice. It also contains a small quantity of Helsinki fragments, causing overlap. In scholarship drawing on the MPO catalogue, the actual number of fragments in Stockholm has consequently been estimated at between 22 700 and 23 000 fragments.⁶⁰ These often-quoted figures, however, do not include the numerous early print fragments – detached from the accounts, removed from the relevant archives, and not included in the MPO – estimated at perhaps 2 500 leaves.⁶¹

In Finland, new estimates on the number of manuscript fragments were produced as the material was digitised in 2008–2011. Based on the metadata work done in conjunction with the digitising, recent scholarship has provided an estimate of 9 400 leaves, i.e. not fragments, for which no precise figure has been available.⁶² As with the Swedish collections, the early print fragments in the Finnish collections are not included in the figures, and their number appears to have not previously been calculated at all.

The research data that we have produced makes it possible to refine both the Swedish and, especially, the Finnish figures. A critical examination of the MPO data shows that it contains a somewhat larger number of duplicate records than has been previously realised. First, the MPO gives metadata for 220 fragments belonging to the Helsinki collection, and they should primarily be considered in that context. Second, it contains at least 106 fragments that were entered twice (or thrice on two occasions), with this duplication mentioned in the metadata. We have also identified 27 fragments that are made of paper and appear not to have constituted a part of a cover and thus should not be included in our calculation. Finally, 124 fragments, which are in Sweden but do not belong to collections systematically covered by the MPO catalogue, are listed.⁶³ Thus, depending on whether researchers choose to include individual fragments from scattered Swedish archives, the number of MPO fragments is at most 22 554 (22 430, if we count only the Stockholm fragments). Since

59 Brunius 2013, 43–44.

60 *Åslaug Ommundsen* and *Tuomas Heikkilä* (2017, 8) place the number of fragments in the Swedish National Archives at 22 700 (ca. 40 000 leaves from ca. 11 000 books); *Jan Brunius* (2013, 36–37) estimates 23 000 fragments and 11 000 books; while, not too much earlier, *Gunilla Björkvall* (2006, 8) provided an estimate of 22 700 fragments – but from only 6 000 books (perhaps referencing the number of CCM codex signa).

61 Wolodarski 2013, 203–4.

62 Ommundsen & Heikkilä 2017, 8.

63 The MPO systematically covers the collections at *Riksarkivet Marieberg* (especially *Kammarkivet*), *Slottsarkivet* and *Krigsarkivet*. The largest fragment entity not belonging to these collections, but included in the MPO, appears to be at Uppsala Universitetsbiblioteket (23 frs).

there may be other, unidentified, duplicates in the MPO, the figure may actually be somewhat lower. The number of covers that the fragments have constituted can only be estimated. Given that, based on our manual calculations of the Helsinki collection, a fragment constitutes approximately 0.9 covers, the number of covers might be projected at 20 300. To this figure, it is possible to also add an estimate of the early print covers (excluding those associated with Finland), for which we can only quote the aforementioned 1 300 covers (or 2 500 leaves).

For Finland, accurate numbers for the collections at the National Library, based on counting the physical collection items, are as follows. The number of manuscript fragments is 5 435 (9 202 leaves). In addition, the National Library holds 996 fragments from early printed parchment books, which also were all originally used as covers for the Finland-related Vasa-era accounts. Thus, when counting fragments of medieval books (both manuscripts and early prints), the present extent of the Helsinki fragment collection housed at the National Library of Finland is 6 431 fragments (or 5 687 covers).

To refine the 'Finnish' figures, we have also tracked down most of the early print fragments, which were used to physically 'reconstruct' copies of *Missale Aboense* and very likely also used to cover Finnish accounts. In addition to one such book in the National Library (included in the above figures), another reconstruction can be found in the Jyväskylä University Library (137 fragments, 120 covers) and another still in Kungliga biblioteket (National Library of Sweden) in Stockholm (95 fragments, 85 covers). For the Jyväskylä copy, the fragments came via Helsinki, but the trail is less clear for the Stockholm copy. It is entirely possible that it includes some leaves from books that remained in Stockholm in the nineteenth century, when the binding was created. Thus, with this slight caveat, the total number of Finland-related (if not Helsinki) fragments could also be estimated at 6 663 fragments (5 892 covers).

Before arriving at our final tally, we must mention those fragments still not accounted for in even the broadest definitions applied to the Stockholm and Helsinki collections. They concern the collections of two libraries outside the Nordic countries. First, the Library of the Russian Academy of Sciences in St. Petersburg holds 166 fragments, which were taken there in 1869 from the Helsinki collections.⁶⁴ Second, the British Library holds an estimated 600 fragments once used to cover Swedish accounts and donated by the linguist and collector *George Stephens* in the nineteenth century.⁶⁵

We can now summarise our findings on the full extent of the Swedish-Finnish fragment collections. According to our data-based calculation, originally close to 37 500 covers made of reused parchment were attached to account

64 Löfstrand 1984, 2.

65 Lehtinen 2005, 111–114.

booklets in one form or another. Approximately 25 750 of these were attached to accounts belonging to the *Landskapshandlingar* account collection, which suffered almost all of the losses resulting from the 1807 fire. The losses amount to approximately 9 250 fragments, i.e. approximately 36 per cent of the covers in the *Landskapshandlingar* collection or 25 per cent of all covers, which leaves us with an estimated 28 250 covers today. While, as we have demonstrated, it has not been possible to simply count the covers made of medieval parchment as they are, we can attempt to verify this figure by contrasting it with an estimate based on studying the archival collections as they are today. If we add together the estimated number of covers in the MPO (20 300), the 'Finnish' collection (5 892), understood broadly, and the uncatalogued Swedish early prints (1 300) as well as the estimated number of covers constituted by the fragments in the British Library (540) and Russian Academy of Sciences (150), we arrive at a total of approximately 28 200 covers – almost the same as above. Given the inherent uncertainties associated with some of the figures, we feel that rounding them to the nearest thousand provides good figures for making general references to the size of the collections, amounting to approximately 37 000 covers made of medieval parchment originally, 9 000 covers lost, and 28 000 covers still existing today.

One issue when estimating the size of the collections are the varying conventions regarding the units (leaf, fragment, cover) used to provide data on them. As we have seen, the ratios can to an extent be estimated. For the relationships between a fragment, a cover, and the number of folia, we can say that a fragment typically represents 0.9 covers and 1.7 folia.⁶⁶ Using these ratios for conversion purposes when more direct data is unavailable, our rounded estimate of all currently existing fragments, using these different units, is 28 000 covers (as mentioned above), 31 500 fragments, and 54 000 folia.⁶⁷

Conclusions

The Stockholm-Helsinki fragment collection is an invaluable body of evidence for research into Nordic book and church history. The goal of this article has been to facilitate its research use by defining the scope of the collections more accurately than previously and by clarifying the relationship between the covers made of recycled parchment and the Vasa-era accounts. We have presented an estimate on the original number of both accounts and fragments in the

66 For instance, there are 5 433 fragments with 9 199 leaves in the *Fragmenta Membranea* amounting to 1.69 leaves per fragment.

67 Our data set enables the direct counting of fragments and leaves, amounting to approximately 29 000 fragments or 50 000 leaves. This, however, leaves out lots of early printed leaves meaning the actual figures are higher.

seventeenth century and traced a path to the present through examining the losses that both types of material suffered in the early nineteenth century, primarily (and perhaps exclusively) in the 1807 fire.

By way of methodology, we hope that this article offers an inspiring exploration of the possibilities offered by quantitative and data-driven approaches to studying the fragments. Our dataset has been compiled using the digital collection metadata as a starting point. We have both parsed and enriched the data and then combined it with data on the archival losses created from other sources. Needless to say, work of this kind was prohibitively laborious before the digital turn of the early twenty-first century, when corpora of collection metadata were not easily accessible for researchers. However, the current situation allows for relatively easy access to sets of metadata, which, given the ubiquitousness of effective tools (i.e. personal computers) for refining such data, makes such approaches inviting, fruitful, and even necessary.

We should also like to underline that, for our particular endeavour, the different data have been much more central than the methods. We have not used any statistical modelling, let alone advanced computing facilities or artificial intelligence. This decision is partly due to our personal skill limitations, but mostly the approach has been defined by our simple research questions. However, simple does not equate with unimportant. Indeed, at least in the humanities, having solid and controlled data can be more important than having access to cutting-edge computational methods. When thinking about data-driven historical scholarship in the broadest sense, some of the most important contributions to the field have undoubtedly been *Thomas Piketty's* *longue-durée* studies of economic history.⁶⁸ While *Piketty* and his collaborators also used proper statistical methods, it is obvious that the important results of their research stem mainly from the extensive data collection and data curation work.⁶⁹ Our topic and our results are much more modest, but they nonetheless demonstrate a similar point: data alone can take you a long way.

To return more concretely to fragment studies, the next step could be using the data on the distribution of the losses to estimate more accurately what kinds of fragments have been lost. The potential of this exercise is best introduced by way of an example. At the same time that we compiled the dataset for the present study, we also created some other data for each fragment: the date of the medieval book that it comes from and the date of its reuse in the sixteenth or seventeenth century. Examining these variables in tandem, we see that the average date of reuse varies according to the dating of the medieval manuscript: the older the manuscript, the earlier it was likely reused. For

68 In particular, see *Piketty* 2013, 2019.

69 Published in the World Inequality Database: <https://wid.world/> [accessed 10 September 2024].

instance, leaves coming from manuscripts dated to before 1225 constituted 24 per cent of the reused covers in the 1560s, but only eight per cent in the first decade of the seventeenth century.⁷⁰ As we have seen, the 1807 fire caused the worst damage to materials from the most voluminous decades of record making, the 1550s and 1560s. Since twelfth- and early thirteenth-century fragments were used intensively in this period, scholars have thus lost many more such fragments than, for instance, fifteenth-century fragments, the reuse of which peaked later. Since we know what proportion of the accounts has survived from a given year, we may even estimate the numbers of lost fragments with relative accuracy.⁷¹ Figure 7 introduces a preliminary example of such a calculation. It shows how fragments used as covers for the Swedish provincial records (which absorbed almost all of the losses) dated to before 1225 are distributed according to the year when they were recycled and how many of them have likely been lost for each year of the account series.

Figure 7: Pre-1225 fragments in the *Landskapshandlingar* collection: originally (projection) and today.⁷²

A similar examination would be entirely possible, for instance, regarding the type of book or province from which the accounts originated. Working gradually in this way, one could eventually create a relatively accurate picture of the

⁷⁰ Based on our project's data on fragments with a dating and a year of reuse provided in the metadata.

⁷¹ This estimate is based on the assumption that the distribution of the material in the lost collection was similar to what survives. Since the surviving entities are proportionately quite large and the losses were entirely random, this assumption seems well founded. More detailed base distributions could also be produced from our data. The datings of the fragments involved have been determined by taking their dating time frames (e.g. the thirteenth century) and converting it into a single numerical value, i.e. the middle point of the time frame.

⁷² Data source: Books of the Medieval Parish Church. Data series: Fragments originally (4 989); fragments today (2 418).

nature of the fragment corpus as it existed before the 1807 fire, and thus move one step closer to understanding the medieval book resources of the Swedish realm. This accomplishment would, in its turn, facilitate attempts to examine the fragments quantitatively in the pursuit of broader research topics, such as the process of Christianisation and parish formation in Sweden and Finland.

Work on the Finnish and Swedish manuscript fragments is presently advancing on several fronts. Traditional textual as well as palaeographical and codicological examinations continue to yield new results, and promising experimentation is simultaneously being undertaken with scientific methods in the study of their materials.⁷³ Quantitative approaches utilising collection metadata offer yet another complementary perspective on this body of sources, from which much can still be learned.

73 See, e.g. Kasso et al. 2023; Supponen 2023; Tahkokallio 2023.

Archival sources

Swedish National Archives

Kammarens ämbetsarkiv, D II Ser I:2 & I:4

Online databases and datasets

Medeltida pergamentsomslag (MPO): <https://sok.riksarkivet.se/MPO>
 Fragmenta membranea (FM): <https://fragmenta.kansalliskirjasto.fi/>
 Nationell arkivdatabas (NAD): <https://sok.riksarkivet.se/nad>
 Ligatus: Language of Bindings: <https://www.ligatus.org.uk/lob/>
 Dataset prepared for this article ('How-many-fragments_dataset'):
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13879587>

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